

DIGITAL ECOSYSTEM FOR THE NEW EUROPEAN BAUHAUS

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Website	https://digiNEB.eu

D2.4 – NEB’s Digital Hub – 3rd release

Work Package	WP2 NEB's Digital Hub
Task	T2.1 NEB Digital Hub setup, maintenance, and evolution
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Quality Officer	Florence Kuijl (InnovaWood)
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X	PU: Public
	SEN: Sensitive
	R-UE/EU-R: EU Classified
	C-UE/EU-C: EU Classified
	S-UE/EU-S: EU Classified

Versioning History

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0.7	14/10/2024	María Tomé Nuez (EAAE)	Peer review
0.8	18/10/2024	Frank van der Hoeven (TU Delft)	Second draft
0.9	30/10/2024	Florence Kuijl (InnovaWood)	Quality Control
1.0	01/11/2024	Frank van der Hoeven (TU Delft)	Final version
1.1	30/03/2025	Frank van der Hoeven (TU Delft)	Update (sustainability)

Glossary of terms

Item	Description
CC-BY	Creative Commons Attribution
CMS	Content Management System
EAAE	European Association for Architectural Education
EAG	External Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
JSON	Java Script Object Notation
NEB	New European Bauhaus
NEBA	New European Bauhaus Alliance
SQL	Structured Query Language
The Consortium	All the Project Partners: TU DELFT + EAAE + ICF + IW
TWG	Thematic Working Group
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Keywords

Website, Directory, CMS, Copyright, Creative Commons, Open Science, Digital Ecosystem

Disclaimer

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Executive Summary

This report provides an overview over the third release of the DigiNEB website. It should be understood that the deliverable itself is the new version of the platform, published early October.

This report was completed afterwards and provides a concise overview over that deliverable. It outlines the starting points for revision 3, describes the new approach to the platform, to provide a detailed overview of the release.

Furthermore, it looks ahead how all methods and instruments can be transferred to the relevant stakeholder groups for continued use.

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1. Starting Points

After a challenging separation process that resulted in the mutually agreed exit of partner Trust-IT from the project, we faced a six-month period during which Trust-IT did not provide access to the digital assets of the DigiNEB project, including the website, social media accounts, mailing list, and URL.

During this time, the consortium began developing a new setup to address several urgent issues identified with the original website:

- **Look and feel of the website not 'NEBBY' enough**

The original site was not sufficiently aligned with the look, feel, or style of other New European Bauhaus (NEB) project websites, which tend to be more creative or artistic ("NEBBY").

- **Inadequate search functionality**

Although we had identified hundreds of digital tools and projects relevant to the New European Bauhaus community, the directories created by Trust-IT lacked adequate search capabilities. Users could only search by title, not by content. If someone already knows the name of what they are looking for, searching in a database becomes unnecessary.

- **Potential copyright infringement**

The directory setup involved creating dedicated pages for each tool or project, which contained text and images taken directly from source websites. This issue was flagged as problematic in the initial ethics report and was later confirmed by the data steward of TU Delft. It affected hundreds of webpages and posed a significant risk of copyright infringement.

- **Scraping of user data**

The initial website setup required users to register and login to access information on specific courses or tools, only to find that these were often just publicly available links. The only function of this additional step appeared to be collecting user data. Trust-IT had furthermore included a clause in the user terms that stated the collected data could be used in similar projects through a soft opt-in: "For future marketing, promotional, and publicity purposes, by sending you direct e-mail marketing communication regarding events hosted and services provided by the website, which are of an identical or similar scope to those you have previously signed up for or acquired via the website ('Soft Opt-in')." The ethics report flagged this soft opt-in as a violation of EU privacy laws.

These four issues listed above is not an exhaustive overview but helps to explain the main steps we took in developing the next release of the platform.

2. A new approach

- **Grav - CMS**

Some of these issues, such as the limited search capabilities, may have been related to our previous platform choice: Drupal. After obtaining the necessary URL's, we restructured the web platform on a new foundation. As our CMS, we chose Grav, a modern, fast, flat-file CMS that doesn't require a MySQL database. All data is stored in Markdown or JSON format.

- **Flex-Objects**

For the directories, we use a plugin called Flex-Objects, which makes it extremely easy to add content and find it in the directory. All text is searchable on the fly, including titles, synopses, URLs, and tags.

- **Removal of Copyright-Protected Content**

The original website created separate pages for each tool, project, or course, containing the same information available on the source sites. We have removed this unnecessary and problematic in-between step. This change reduces the number of clicks required for users to access the content they're looking for, streamlines the website, and makes it easier to maintain (we removed 250+ pages). Above all, it eliminates potential copyright-infringing material from the site.

- **Tool and Project Suggestions by Email**

We have removed the requirement to register in order to add or access content on the platform. All information is now freely accessible without the need to log in, creating a barrier-free experience. Users can suggest content using suggestion forms protected by reCAPTCHA. Anyone can use their own or an anonymized email address to suggest a tool or project. We do not store personal information on the platform, except for the publicly available user profiles for EAB members, early adopters, and contributing staff.

- **Alignment with NEB Alliance**

In our initial roadmap, we envisioned that the NEB Academy could build on the achievements of the DigiNEB project. Three out of four partners are now continuing within the NEB Alliance, a project tasked with developing the NEB Academy. DigiNEB and NEBA now use the same web solutions (such as Grav CMS) for their platforms and are closely aligned in their efforts.

- **Typography and Imagery**

The new website features improved typography.

The removal of logos and other copyright-protected material required a new approach to visual materials and color schemes.

- **Podcasts**

A new element of the web platform is the integration of over 60 podcasts discussing New European Bauhaus-related topics. These podcasts were specifically recorded in the context of the DigiNEB project and can be explored based on interviewees or by specific topics.

- **Combining Directories and Collections**

Identifying digital projects and tools is essential to the DigiNEB project. During our research, we observed that smaller, isolated collections of content exist and deserve to be included as well. Not all content from these sources fits into our directories—such as tools or projects that do not focus on digital innovation or have a strong proprietary approach. Still, our audience may benefit from a broader scope at this point. Listing these collections makes therefore perfect sense. Initially, we presented our directories and the source collections on separate pages, but in the latest release, they have been integrated into a single page.

- **Security**

Cloudflare provides the security of the platform. Cloudflare is built with data protection in mind as a privacy-first company with end-to-end encryption. Cloudflare complies with local regulations for data locality and storage. They do not generate revenue from advertising, and thus default against the collection and retention of personal data they process on our behalf.

3. Specifications

CMS: Grav 3.7

PHP: 8.1

Data: Markdown, JSON

Operating system: macOS Ventura

Framework: Gantry 5.5

Audio: Soundcloud

Rights: CC-BY 4.0

Security: Cloudflare

An overview of the main pages of the website are provided using screen-prints on a tablet. All pages are fully responsible for mobile phone, tablet, laptop and desktop.

4. Directory taxonomy

The setup of the directories used for listing digital tools and projects use is simple and straight forward. It uses the flex-objects plugin for Grav that allows a free setup with any field that is necessary. It results in a clear form in the backend and an automated display in the frontend.

For the tools and projects, we have used the following fields:

- Name (tool, project)
 - Synopsis
 - Website URL
 - Tags
-
- The initial clustering of tools and projects (*D2.3- Landscape report and gap analysis – preliminary version*) resulted in a comprehensive taxonomy:
 - **Parametric design**
 - **Community**
 - **Training/Skills**
 - **BIM/Digital Twins**
 - Artificial Intelligence
 - Data/Digital/Monitoring
 - Energy
 - Platforms/Networks
 - Smart/IoT

The taxonomy is used as tags to allow easy grouping of both tools and projects. Additional tags are used when the synopsis doesn't capture the full extent of the content.

All data is stored in JSON (Java Script Object Notation).

Screenshots of the backend and frontend of the website shows the setup of the flex-objects.

The screenshot shows a mobile browser interface for the DigiNEB platform. At the top, the browser status bar shows the time 21:12, date Wed 16 Oct, and battery level at 61%. The address bar displays the URL digineb.eu. The page title is "[NEW] Tool name". There are "Back" and "Save" buttons in the top right corner. A teal banner indicates the save location: "Save location: user/data/flex-objects/toolkit.json [NEW]". The form contains the following fields: "Published" with a "Yes/No" toggle (set to "Yes"), "Tool Name" (required, marked with a red asterisk), "Synopsis" (required, marked with a red asterisk), "Website URL", and "Tags". Below the form, there are radio buttons for "After Save..." actions: "Create New Item", "Edit Item" (selected), and "List Items". A teal banner at the bottom of the form area says "Found an issue? Please report it on GitHub." At the very bottom of the page, a footer reads "Grav v1.7.46 - Admin v1.10.46 - was made with ❤️ by Trilby Media."

21:11 Wed 16 Oct 61%

digineb.eu

Digital Tools

[Back](#)
[Export](#)
[Add](#)

Save location: `user/data/flex-objects/toolkit.json`

15

Publ Tool Name	Synopsis	Website URL	Tags	Actions
✓ VOLUM3	VOLUM3 enables co...	https://volum3.com	["platform"]	...
✓ Ladybug	Performs detailed an...	https://www.ladyb...	["Ladybugtools", "Gr...	...
✓ Honeybee	Creates, runs, and vi...	https://www.ladyb...	["Ladybugtools", "Gr...	...
✓ Butterfly	A plugin and a pytho...	https://www.ladyb...	["Ladybugtools", "Pyt...	...
✓ Dragonfly	Dragonfly enables th...	https://www.ladyb...	["Ladybugtools", "Gr...	...
✓ TIE for Rhino	TIE (Tensegrity Integr...	https://publish.illin...	["Rhino", "parametric...	...
✓ Jellyfish	Provides an intuitive ...	https://parametric...	["Grasshopper", "par...	...
✓ GluLamb	A toolkit for modellin...	https://www.food...	["Rhino", "parametric...	...
✓ Starfish	Allows parametric ge...	https://parametric...	["Grasshopper", "par...	...
✓ Wallacei	An Evolutionary Multi...	https://www.walla...	["Grasshopper", "Rhi...	...
✓ Pufferfish	A set of 330 compon...	https://www.food...	["Rhino", "Grasshopp...	...
✓ Rabbit	An open-source plug...	https://morphoco...	["Grasshopper", "par...	...
✓ RhinoVAULT	Provides an intuitive,...	https://blockresea...	["Python", "Rhino", "G...	...
✓ Usercentricity Servic...	This toolkit consists ...	https://www.userc...	["community", "userc...	...
✓ Usercentricity Servic...	What are the best ex...	https://www.userc...	["community", "userc...	...

« < 1 2 3 4 5 > »

Displaying 1 to 15 out of 138 records

Found an issue? Please report it on GitHub.

Grav v1.7.46 - Admin v1.10.46 - was made with by Trilby Media.

VOLUM3

VOLUM3 enables construction professionals to collaborate on projects from any Internet-connected device with access to all project documents, contracts, RFIs, submittals, schedules, drawings and more.

platform

Ladybug

Performs detailed analysis of climate data to produce customized, interactive visualizations for environmentally-informed design.

Ladybugtools Grasshopper parametric design

Honeybee

Creates, runs, and visualizes daylight simulations using Radiance and energy models using OpenStudio and EnergyPlus.

Ladybugtools Grasshopper parametric design

Butterfly

A plugin and a python library to create and run advanced computational fluid dynamic (CFD) simulations using OpenFOAM.

Ladybugtools Python Grasshopper parametric design

Dragonfly

Dragonfly enables the creation of district-scale models for energy simulation with URBANopt, electrical infrastructure simulation with OpenDSS, renewables optimization with REopt, and urban heat island modeling with the Urban Weather Generator (UWG).

Ladybugtools Grasshopper parametric design

TIE for Rhino

TIE (Tensegrity Integration Element) for Rhino is a tool to design tensegrity structure system. Tensegrity structure is composed by cable and strut. The cable of the structure is under tension and the struts are under compression. Among Tensegrity structure system, Simplex and Rhombic system, were chosen to develop for this tool.

Rhino parametric design

Jellyfish

Provides an intuitive and fast way to model, manipulate and visualize implicit geometries

GluLamb

A toolkit for modelling free-form timber structures creating straight, single-curved

Starfish

Allows parametric generation of various patterns, focussing on 2d tessellations that can be

5. Homepage

The home page provides direct access to all the content in the site.

It contains the following sections:

- Menu
- Slider
- The DigiNEB initiative (with direct links to the main content)
- Call to action (tool of project suggestion)
- News Items
- Featured tool
- Event images
- Podcasts
- The DigiNEB partnership (direct links to the partner websites)
- Footer with content that appears on each page

... on Judicious, Unbiased, Safe, and Transparent (JUST) Data

JUST Industry Data Week at the Linköping Science Park, 16-21 September 2024

> MTF Labs

THE DigiNEB INITIATIVE

Digital Tools

Digital Tools for

Digital Projects

Projects that develop

E-learning

E-learning and training

Open Licences

Open Licenses for

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THE DigiNEB INITIATIVE

Digital Tools

Digital Tools for Architects, Designers and Communities

Digital Tools

Digital Projects

Projects that develop Digital Tools or Innovations that can support the Objectives of NEB

Digital Projects

E-learning

E-learning and training modules

E-learning

Open Licences

Open Licences for Data and Content that can be freely used, modified, and shared

Open Licences

If your tool or project is "NEBBY", suggest it to us to have it included in our directory.

SUGGEST YOUR TOOL OR PROJECT

NEWS ITEMS

NEB Call for proposals

~~Just Data~~

Have your say on the New

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NEWS ITEMS

NEB Call for proposals

October 08, 2024

New call for proposals under the NEB programme opened on the 7th of May. The Topics are: Setting up a New European Bauhaus hub for results and impact. New governance models for the co-design and co-construction of public spaces in neighbourhoods by communities, Exploiting the potential of secondary bio-based products. The deadline: 19 September 2024

[Read More...](#)

Just Data Annotation

October 08, 2024

MTF Labs has partnered with the Industry Commons Foundation on a new initiative to create JUST Data annotation standards. The project is funded by the Swedish Innovation Agency Vinnova and sets out to create standards for data practices that aim to be Judicious, Unbiased, Safe, and Transparent.

[Read More...](#)

Have your say on the New European Bauhaus Facility

October 08, 2024

Contribute to the consultation initiated by the European Commission on defining the content of the New European Bauhaus Facility by giving feedback on the Questionnaire on the next NEB Facility, which addresses two components: the research and innovation component the roll-out component. T...

[Read More...](#)

FEATURED TOOL

Volume3

Make sure your design is being built
VOLUM3 integrates all the functions you need: digital plans, tasks and reports, meeting minutes and follow-up, specifications...

Track changes on your project from concept to construction site, all on one easy online platform.

The info is available to you at any time, from multiple devices. Organise your projects in teams, by disciplines and stages — mirroring your real-life workflow.

Sign up, it's free!

EVENTS

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THE DigiNEB PARTNERSHIP

DigiNEB

DigiNEB supports the community of the New European Bauhaus (NEB) with a fine collection of digital solutions, projects and tools.

Funded by the European Union

Contact

Online

Contact

X

Address

LinkedIn

Coordinator

© 2023 - 2024 Copyright by DigiNEB

6. Digital Tools / Digital Project

The Digital Tools and Digital Projects pages provides access to the collections and the directory.

It contains the following sections:

- Menu
- Slider
- Collections
- Directory
- Footer

Digital Tools

A collection of databases of digital tools for architects, designers and communities.

DIGITAL TOOLS - COLLECTIONS

ArchitizerTech

Top tech tools for architects

Architizer

B.GREEN Handbook

Digital Tools for Planners

Handbook

Datascape

Tools to help decision-makers, architects, urban designers and planners interactively explore the wishes and challenges of a local population in an area.

Democracy Technologies

A collection of digital tools for citizen participation, i-voting, and more

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digineb.eu
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DIGITAL TOOLS - COLLECTIONS

ArchitizerTech

Top tech tools for architects

Architizer

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Democracy Technologies

DigiPedia

Digital repository of course material, tutorials and software documentation

DigiPedia

Food4Rhino

Parametric design apps for Rhino and Grasshopper

Food4Rhino

Mobility Data Space

The Mobility Data Space (MDS) brings together companies, organisations and institutions: those who need data for innovative mobility solutions and those who want to monetise their data assets.

Mobility Data Space

OSArch

AEC Free Software directory

OSArch

DIGITAL TOOLS - DIRECTORY

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DIGITAL TOOLS - DIRECTORY

Sort by tool name ↑

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Rhino parametric design

Digital Projects

A collection of databases with projects that develop digital tools or innovations that can support the objectives of the New European Bauhaus: beautiful, sustainable and together.

DIGITAL PROJECTS - COLLECTIONS

European Construction Technology Platform

Digital Built Environment | Project Database List

RI.SE

Projects by the Research Institutes of Sweden

RI SE

Digital Built Britain

Legacy of the achievements of digital built Britain

Digital Built Britain

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DIGITAL PROJECTS - COLLECTIONS

European Construction Technology Platform

Digital Built Environment | Project Database List

ECTP

RI.SE

Projects by the Research Institutes of Sweden

RI.SE

Digital Built Britain

Legacy of the achievements of digital built Britain

Digital Built Britain

DIGITAL PROJECTS - DIRECTORY

Search by project name, full text or tag

Sort by project name ↑

DigiNEB

digiNEB supports the New European Bauhaus (NEB) community with digital solutions, projects and tools while transferring the NEB perspective to the world of digital innovation.

EU-funded Digital Europe NEB

UserCentriCities

A platform for local authorities to compare their performance with their peers and exchange mutual learning about how to deliver user-centric services

community EU-funded Horizon2020

Digidem Lab

an independent democracy lab that supports neighbourhoods, municipalities and public institutions in conducting effective and inclusive citizen dialogues through "Participatory Budget and Citizen Participation", "Community organising", "Civic Tech and Digital Development", "Citizens' assembly"

community

7. New European Bauhaus

The NEB page provides access to lighthouse projects, prizes, EIT projects and NEB labs. Examples of these pages are provided.

THE NEW EUROPEAN BAUHAUS INITIATIVE

NEB PROJECTS, PRIZES AND LABS

The New European Bauhaus (NEB) is a creative and interdisciplinary initiative that connects the European Green Deal to our living spaces and experiences. NEB supports through various EU programmes and national initiatives a broad range of projects, prizes and partnerships that are categorised below.

NEB Lighthouse projects

NEB Prizes

EIT Enhance NEB

NEB labs

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Lighthouse projects

These projects create more sustainable, inclusive, and beautiful spaces in 13 locations across the European Union and beyond, and involve citizens in the green transition at the local level.

HORIZON-MISS-2021-NEB-01-01

NEBourhoods

Creating NEBourhoods Together ensures sustainable living and working in the Munich district of Neuperlach. Together with citizens, creative people and experts, we develop ideas in and for Neuperlach.

NEBourhoods

Cultuur&Campus

Rotterdam is the city that always looks forward, where we see plenty of space and seize that space. The city that doesn't live, think, or act in boxes. Where we connect and strengthen unique powers. And thus go beyond the boundaries of what one can imagine alone.

Cultuur&Campus

The Living Corridor

By the end of 2021, 50 m2 of container gardens will be installed in green areas surrounding the Department of Management (University of Turin). Environmental sustainability, but also inclusion and urban regeneration are at the heart of the project.

The Living Corridor

Play AUT the Box

Play AUT the Box, Playable cities for all (PATB) builds on ASD Publics to reinforce and go one step further in the improvement of public play spaces for children with autism and their families.

Play AUT the Box

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NEB Labs

The NEB Lab is a co-creation space at the service of the New European Bauhaus community, for the delivery of beautiful, sustainable, and inclusive projects to improve our daily lives.

[The NEB Lab](#)

Nordic carbon neutral Bauhaus

Nordic authorities have already established an active collaboration for preparing effective and practical policies for sustainable construction. Regular activities include Nordic stakeholder meetings and Nordic Climate Forum for Construction, held every year.

[Nordic Bauhaus](#)

New European Bauhaus on the Danube

The NEW EUROPEAN BAUHAUS investigates how to seriously support and drive resilient development in Danube territories. The lab brings together a transdisciplinary pool of decision makers, urbanists, artists and activists, business leaders, finance experts, academics and NGOs from the region.

[Danube Future Works](#)

New European Bauhaus Prizes

NEW EUROPEAN BAUHAUS PRIZES

PRIZES AWARDED UP TO EUR 30,000

The Prizes recognise and reward existing projects and young people’s concepts, which demonstrate that the sustainable solutions promoted by the European Green Deal can also be inclusive and beautiful, bringing high-quality experiences to people's everyday lives.

NEB Prizes 2021

NEB Prizes 2022

NEB Prizes 2023

8. DigiNEB Project

The DigiNEB Project landing page provides access to the goals, partnership and network.

It contains the following sections:

- Menu
- Goals
- Network (including External Advisory Board, Digital Focus Groups, Early Adopters and Podcasts)
- Footer

Example pages are provided for a DigiNEB Partner (including staff members), an External Advisory Board (EAB) member, an Early Adopter. Landing pages for the EAB and the Early Adopters will be provided similar to the overview of Interviewees in the podcast series. Podcast can be selected based on interviewee and on the topics that they address.

GOALS

DigiNEB fosters digital solutions that boosts the growing New European Bauhaus (NEB) movement. It bridges the digital and NEB communities and raises awareness around digital solutions for all NEB stakeholders. With its lean action plan, DigiNEB enables Europe's Green Deal ambition in designing & building greener and more inclusive living spaces for a better quality of life.

Map & showcase

Digital solutions, projects & tools, capitalising on EU-funded initiatives

Create a community

Facilitating cooperation between ICT and NEB stakeholders through workshops, events, networking

Produce capacity building material

Showcase identified best practice uses of digital technologies for NEB

Elaborate joint policy recommendations

A NEB Digital Deployment Roadmap based on the input of Digital Focus Groups

THE DigiNEB PARTNERSHIP

Four great partners jointly working on digital solutions for the New European Bauhaus.

TU Delft

TU DELFT (NL, Coordinator), 1st in the EU and 3rd world-wide in the QS field specific ranking for Architecture | Built Environment

ICF

ICF (SE), an extensive network of 8,000 creative innovators and experts in cross-domain collaboration

EAAE

EAAE (BE), an international, membership-based Association organising architectural schools in Europe

InnovaWood

InnovaWood (BE), the main European network for forest & wood science, innovation and education

NETWORK

We can't scout for digital solutions alone and we don't do it for ourselves.

External Advisory Board

Digital Focus Groups

Podcasts

Early Adopters

[Go to the episodes ...](#)

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digineb.eu

DIGINEB Digital ▾ NEB ▾ **DigiNEB ▾** Podcasts ▾ News

EAAE

European Association for Architectural Education (BE), an international, membership-based Association organising architectural schools in Europe

[> EAAE](#)

The European Association for Architectural Education is an international, membership-based Association organizing architectural schools in Europe. Membership is not limited to countries that belong to the European Union, all European countries may participate. The EAAE is a non-profit, Belgian registered organization.

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Roberto Cavallo

Mar Muñoz Aparici

Alan Organschi is a principal and partner at [Gray Organschi Architecture](#), an architectural practice in New Haven, Connecticut, recognized internationally for its integration of design, construction, and environmental research. He is also the founder of the fabrication workshop and construction management firm JIG Design Build which in 2018 created the Ecological Living Module, a fully self-sustaining micro house for the United Nations Environment Program.

In April 2021, Alan was appointed Director of the Innovation Lab at [the Bauhaus der Erde](#) a global interdisciplinary initiative that seeks to transform the building sector from a major source of anthropogenic environmental and social impact into a regenerative and ecologically sensitive means to meet the housing and infrastructural needs of an urbanizing global population. In that capacity, he directs the development of the Lab, its experimental projects, public programs and trans-sectoral collaborations with global partners.

He continues as a Senior member of the faculty at the Yale School of Architecture where he has taught architectural design and building technology for two decades. During the 2019 and 2020 academic years, he also served as the Portman Critic at the Georgia Institute of Technology School of Architecture. The findings of the research and design work of the studios he conducted were published in the two-volume collection entitled Technosphere/Biosphere.

His ongoing research project, the [Timber City Initiative](#), examines the application of emerging structural wood fiber technologies to the construction of global cities. Timber City has been awarded

Christopher Morris is an architect at Arkkitehtitoimisto ALA Oy in Helsinki, who is making waves in the field of sustainable architecture. Currently serving as the project architect for Satama Areena, a groundbreaking development featuring the largest hanging wooden roof in the Nordics, Morris is at the forefront of utilizing innovative timber design techniques and promoting collaborative approaches across all design disciplines.

Driven by a deep passion for timber design, Morris is committed to pushing the boundaries of what is possible with sustainable building materials. With a keen eye for innovation and a belief in the power of interdisciplinary collaboration, they envision a European future where timber plays a central role in constructing environmentally friendly and visually striking architectural marvels.

At Arkkitehtitoimisto ALA Oy, Morris actively advocates for joint solutions that bring together various design disciplines. By fostering collaboration between architects, engineers, and other experts, Morris aims to unlock new possibilities and advance the use of timber in European construction projects. This approach not only ensures the structural integrity and safety of timber-based designs but also maximizes their potential for creating sustainable, efficient, and visually captivating spaces.

NEB Concepts

NEB Concepts features insightful conversations with leading architects, educators, and project leaders. The discussions deal with topics at the intersection of sustainability, innovation, and human-centred design. You'll hear directly from those shaping the future of urban development, cultural heritage, and community empowerment.

NEB Concepts is modular – it allows you to 'choose your own adventure': follow the links and tags to explore themes such as climate adaptation, technology integration, and interdisciplinary collaboration – or stick with the wide-ranging thoughts of a single interviewee.

Each short episode provides a collection of ideas and practices, projects and reflections, highlighting the transformative potential of the New European Bauhaus for a more inclusive and sustainable future.

The interviewees

- DIGINEB
- Digital ▾
- NEB ▾
- DigiNEB ▾
- Podcasts ▾**
- News

Francesca Rizzo - Part 1

- New European Bauhaus
- Sustainability
- Inclusion
- Human-centered design
- Community engagement
- Ecosystem approach

Francesca Rizzo - Part 2

- Human-centered design
- Urban design and development
- Nature-based solutions
- Community engagement
- Cultural heritage and diversity

Topic: Urban design and development

Davor Meersman - Part 2

New European Bauhaus
Urban design and development

Davor Meersman - Part 4

Sustainability
Urban design and development

9. News

The News page is straight forward. News Items are presented as 'cards'. An example of a full news item is provided.

The news page contains the following sections:

- Menu
- News
- Footer

-
- Digital ▾
- NEB ▾
- DigiNEB ▾
- Podcasts ▾
- News

20th EU Region Week

10-13.10.2022 | EU Region Week | Brussels, Belgium The European Week of Regions and Cities (EU Region Week 2022) is the biggest annual Brussels-based event ded...

ACE/EAAE Conference & Third EAAE Deans' Summit

20-21.04.2023 | ACE/EAAE | Brussels, Belgium How can architects take up a role when things become difficult? In times of political uncertainty, inhabiting a fra...

Call for partners

The New European Bauhaus supports a movement of sustainable communities, inclusive dialogues, and purposeful activities. The role of partners is to help build ...

Building the bioeconomy with nature-based materials and solutions within the New European

DigiNEB workshop at CA²RE

11-13.04.2024 | CA²RE | Valencia, Spain The CA²RE Community (Conferences for

CA²RE Valencia: Experimentation

11-13.04.2024 | CA²RE | Valencia, Spain This edition of CA²RE proposes to explore the concept of

20th EU Region Week

/ [EVENT](#), [EUROPEAN WEEK OF REGIONS AND CITIES](#)

10-13.10.2022 | EU Region Week | Brussels, Belgium

The European Week of Regions and Cities (EU Region Week 2022) is the biggest annual Brussels-based event dedicated to cohesion policy bringing together regions and cities from all over Europe, including politicians, administrators, experts and academics.

EU Post-Pandemic Cohesion Policy

This year's edition focuses on cohesion policy and the EU's financial instruments for tackling the COVID-19 crisis, supporting a socially fair recovery, and successfully managing the green and digital transition.

digINEB.eu at EU Region Week 2022

digINEB.eu project member and ~~NEB High Level Round Table~~ member Michela Magas is

digINEB – Digital ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus initiative has received funding from the European Union's Digital Europe Programme (DIGITAL) under Grant Agreement no. 101083743.

10. Sustainability and reflection

The DoA of the DigiNEB project calls specifically for a sustainability plan as part of task 5.3:

“...The task will define the long-term sustainability approach by ensuring that all methods and instruments are transferred to the relevant stakeholder groups for continued use.” [2]

The choice for a flat-file CMS makes the DigiNEB platform extremely flexible and easy to move to a next hosting environment as it doesn't require a database. The DigiNEB platform is one folder. One places it in a hosting environment and it runs, both online and locally.

TU Delft is committed to maintain the platform for the next five years, or until the point that the content is merged into the next initiative.

There is a real perspective for such a merger. The core of the DigiNEB consortium continues its work in the NEBA Alliance, the EU funded project to prepare the so-called New European Bauhaus (NEB) Academy.

We have included in the scope of this project:

+Bio-based

+Circular

+Regenerative

+Long-life

+Digital

Digital is explicitly included in the work and the scope of the NEB Academy in order to ensure that all methods and instruments identified in the DigiNEB project are transferred to the relevant stakeholder groups for continued use.

The setup of the NEBA web-platform uses by design the same CMS and the same plugins as the DigiNEB platform. This allows us to port with minimal effort the methods and instruments into the NEBA environment. We are currently considering the question how and where the work done in the DigiNEB project is best positioned.

With minimal effort we can maintain the DigiNEB platform and expand it continuously.

But... central in the DigiNEB approach is to build an index of hundreds of digital tools and projects. In our discussions on how to move forward we don't question if trying to double that effort in the coming years will be impactful. No firm, institute, course or individual uses in practice hundreds of tools to complete tasks, make designs or teach assignments.

One promising alternative approach that the NEB Academy offers is to go for quality instead of quantity. By selecting the best and most flexible tools, to document how to install and use these, and by describing workflows how various tools together can help to perform complex tasks, we might be of better assistance to the New European Bauhaus community.

TU Delft has built an online and blended learning environment (DigiPedia) that will be used as LMS in the NEB Academy that will be used to do just that. This means that the conditions are set to ensure continued use of the achievements of the DigiNEB project.

